

Varietal analyze of chemical composition moisture, ash and sugar of date palm fruits

Mallah N.A.¹, Sahito H.A.^{1*}, K.ousar T.¹, Kubar W.A.¹, Jatoi F.A.¹, Shah Z.H.¹, Mangrio W.M.¹

¹ Department of Zoology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Pakistan.

*Corresponding author: Sahito HA, Ph. #. +92 (0) 301-3515723; E-mail: hakim.sahito@salu.edu.pk

Received: April 24, 2017, Accepted: May 29, 2017, Published: May 29, 2017.

ABSTRACT:

The date palm fruit is a very important source of nutrients and cash crop of Sindh, Pakistan due to ideal climatic conditions for its cultivation. There are many varieties of date palm cultivated in region, Sindh but commercially important varieties are Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli and Dadhi in relation to sugar, moisture and ash contents. These different varieties were kept under observation in laboratory conditions from August, 2016 to April, 2017. The highest sugar content and moisture percentage observed in Kupro 85.90% and 23% whereas; lowest percentage was 65.50% and 10% in Aseel and Dadhi dry varieties, respectively. Thus, the date palm fruit is known as a potential in various aspects of proteins for the better human body to control the different diseases and support the metabolism process. Therefore, it is recommended to use for the better human health because of attraction of high sugar and moisture contents.

Keyword: *Nutritional value, moisture, ash, sugar and P. dactylifera.*

INTRODUCTION

The history of date palm was as old as man which is also considered as an oldest tree on the earth planet [1, 2]. The exact origin of date palm trees is unknown, but it is believed those have occurred naturally in the region of the Persian bay. It was abundant predominantly between the Nile and Euphrates rivers. The earliest references of date's fruit can be found in the Mesopotamian culture in the region of Iraq and Indus civilization. In Mesopotamia (now Iraq) date-palm has been cultured as early as 5000 B.C. [3]. The storage vases of Moen-Jo-Daro point out the civilization of date palm in Sindh is about 2000 B.C. ancient, [4]. Date palm fruit is also mentioned in the Bible (Injeel) and the Holy Quran. In Bible it is mentioned over 50 times and also referred as the "tree of life". While in the Holy Quran it has been referred to over 20 times and in many Ahadiths. It being a tasty and good is considered as a Paradise fruit in Holy Quran. The yield of Date palm is the significant in hot and semi-arid areas of the earth. It is cultivated mainly in Asia and Africa including some parts of Europe and USA. It plays a basic and fundamental role in the financial system and social life in these regions. The date's fruit has forever been great value almost in all cultures and religions of the humankind. Whole Muslim societies in the region of the world presently numbering 1.6 billion peoples are consumer of dates. Consumption of Dates is high during Christian festival as well as in Ramadan month. Correspondingly, the date's fruit enjoys huge importance on the events of Divali and such festivals in other religions. Standard sales of dates are broaden a period from October to April.

Date palm is multi-purpose tree and its all parts are used. It provides food (dates fruit), shelter and timber products [5]. The date palm fruit is made up of a seed and flesh, which constitutes between 80 to 88% of date fruit weight [6]. Dates have great percentage of nutrients such as sugar, minerals and vitamins etc, while there is no cholesterol in them [7]. Dates are fulfill with energy due to presence of high percentage of simple sugar (70-80%) [8]. However, dates being a less supplementation protein value, so its requirement will be completed when these are used at

high levels in the diet. According to economic value the date's fruit is the largest part of food and it is energetic diet [9]. Soft, semi-dry and dry dates are eaten as whole fruit. Dates are used to all over the world as high nutritive and energy supplying food. The most peoples in Saudi Arabia used dates as a part of food and any event is not celebrated without Saudi dates. Fresh dates are so soft and easily digestible with simple sugar that is why, by eating these quickly supply energy to the body; thus due to these qualities fresh dates are being used to during the month of Ramadan. The peak season for date's consumption is also Ramadan month, over all the Muslim countries of the world.

The physical and chemical characters of date's fruit were observed by [10] the fruit flesh weight, thickness of the flesh and pit weight on the physical basis. On the chemical basis he observed the carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals, vitamins and crude fibers. The susceptibility of some dry date-palm varieties to infestation by saw tooth grain beetle in relation to their chemical composition [11]. The pests ravage red date palm trees as well as date palm production in Pakistan [12]. Dates fruit being a sweet it is most nutritious 2500-3000 calories/kg supplying food. It is used as a staple food because the ripped dates content about 80% sugar [13]. Chemical analysis of flesh of two varieties of date palm fruit (Deglet nour and Alig) analyzed and these varieties were cultivated in Djerid region (Oasis of Tozeur, Tunisia) [14]. Total sugar was analyzed by HPLC method and mineral elements were measured by atomic absorption photometer. Therefore, here the goal of present study is to observe the affect on the nutritional value of different semi-dry and dry date fruit varieties of Sindh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

Two districts of Sindh Province, Khairpur Mir's and Sukkur were selected for the proposed research.

Fig. 1. Map of Sindh showing district Khairpur and Sukkur Selected Date palm varieties

The different stored Date palm fruit varieties such as semi-dry date varieties i.e. Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli and dry date varieties i.e., Aseel and Dadhi were selected during, 2016-17. The reason of selection of these varieties was upon some of the prominent characters such as these give huge amount of yield, have great economic values and have high percentage of sugar. For these values, the local agriculture organization industries and date palm industries are promoting them in those areas.

Fig. 2. Showing Date palm fruit varieties Sampling and chemical analysis

The samples of ripped and stored fruit of different varieties of date palm such as; Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli (semi-dry dates) and Aseel & Dadhi (dry dates) were collected in the month of August and September from the stores, market and Mandy of Khairpur Mir's and Sukkur Sindh, Pakistan, were analyzed for the determination of Moisture, Ash and Sugar. After collection, the fruit of date palm was cut, de-seeded and the pulp (flesh) portion was also homogenized in the blender for analysis. Reagents (substance/mixture) used of analytical trade available in the laboratory. The double distilled and deionizer water prepared in the laboratory was used throughout the work. Three parameters moisture, ash and carbohydrate (sugar) were analyzed according to [15].

Determination of moisture

The percentage of moisture was determined by weighing the mass of a food before and after the water removed by evaporation according [16, 17]. The equipments were needed such as; Electric weigh machine, Electric oven and Petri-dishes.

Procedure

First of all, the measured the weight 20 grams of every variety of dates samples by electric weigh machine and then those samples were put in Petri-dishes. The moisture content of the samples was observed by drying samples in an electric oven at 110°C over a night till constant weight obtained. The loss in weight after drying is moisture. The difference in the initial and final weights gave the moisture content. The dry weight was determined by drying in an

air oven at 110°C for one day [15]. The moisture (water) content was calculated as following formula [18].

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Determination of ash

The samples are ignited (heated) at 800 °c to burn off all the organic matters. The inorganic carbon free substance which remains at that temperature is called ash. The following equipments were needed such as; Electric weigh machine, Porcelain crucibles and Muffle furnace.

Procedure

Before weight the samples then put in clean crucibles in a muffle furnace and heated (ignited) at 800°C for 6 an hour. After this all the volatile material escaped, leaving only the non-volatile material than the switch off the muffle furnace. Weigh the crucibles; add the samples in crucibles and weight against difference, the weight of samples can be obtained. Ash samples may be kept for mineral determination. The following formula was used to calculate the percentage (%) of ash (insoluble residue).

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Determination of total sugar

The determination of total sugar was adopted from the phenol-sulphuric acid method as described by [19]. The equipments were used for the analysis of total sugar such as; Mortar and Pestle, Funnel and Conical Flask, Cheese cloth and Filter paper, Tubes and Piped Fluid, Volume Slender, Phenol solution, Sulphuric acid, Sample solution and Spectrophotometer.

Procedure

The 20 grams were measured of every date's variety. Those samples were one by one grinded in mortar by the help of pestle with distilled water (30ml) till to make complete pest. The grinded dates (pest) samples then filtered twice through the cheese cloth and again two times filtered by filter paper while preparing a solution. The solution of every sample (1 ml) was mixed with 1 ml phenol solution, and then added 5 ml concentrated sulphuric acid. Then samples were put at room temperature for half an hour, prior to measuring the absorbance at 485 nm using a spectrophotometer (Ultrospec, 2800). The empty whole was made by substituting of boiled water for the test solution. The concentration of test solution was calculated from calibration curve prepared by the same manner as test solution using glucose as standard.

RESULTS

Chemical Analysis of date flesh of different varieties

Due to the chemical properties, dates have the great market value. They are considered an important in grading, quality, preservation, storage and processing of dates.

Moisture

During present study we observed chemical composition in grams of different flesh date varieties such as, Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli (semi-dry dates) and Aseel, Dadhi (dry dates) contained 23, 20, 15, 14, 10, 10% moisture, respectively (Fig. 1). Fruit of Aseel date palm variety was stored in two forms, the semi-dry date (Khajoor) as well as dry date (Chuhara) form. The maximum moisture was found in Kupro semi-dry date variety 23% and minimum moisture in Aseel and Dadhi dry varieties 10%. It means the semi-dry dates have higher moisture than dry date's varieties. The moisture actually, is one of the fundamental components of fruit which affects basically its quality and acts on preservation. Definitely, this less content in moisture of studied varieties permits

a better conservation, protection and inhibits the development of bacteria and fungi.

Ash

The ash content in Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli (semi-dry date varieties) and Aseel, Dadhi (dry varieties), was 1.35, 1.80, 1.95, 1.40, 1.70, 1.65, respectively (Fig. 2). The Aseel semi-dry date variety was contain the highest percentage of ash but the lowest percentage of ash was recorded in Kupro semi-dry date variety. The fruit of semi-dry Aseel date variety contain high percentage of ash compared to dry Aseel date variety.

Total sugar

The total sugar content in Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasli (semi-dry dates) and Aseel, Dadhi (dry dates), was observed 85.90%, 80.55%, 73.35%, 70.80%, 65.50%, 65.50%, respectively (Fig. 3). The flesh of semi-dry date Kupro variety showed a higher percentage of total sugar content 85.90% than dry date varieties Aseel and Dadhi 65.50%.

Fig.1. Showing percentage of Moisture in different date fruit varieties

Fig. 2. Showing percentage of Ash in different date fruit varieties

Fig. 3. Showing percentage of total Sugar in different date fruit varieties

DISCUSSION

Present study was based on chemical analysis of different stored date palm fruit varieties such as moisture, ash and total sugar were observed in laboratory. Aseel is one main of the varieties, which is cultivated in upper Sindh areas, Pakistan. It is being a good qualities, it has been exported to Asian countries. This variety is stored in two forms one is semi-dry form (Khajoor) and other is dry form (Chuhara) that is why, this variety is also called as the queen of all varieties [20, 21]. Many farmers reap and collect Aseel variety during before maturing stage (Khalal) and boil its fruit to make dry dates called “Chuhara” otherwise; about half of the fruits will be destroyed and spoiled, if there is monsoon rain [22]. This same Aseel variety was harvested at ripening tamar stage to make semi-dry date “Khajoor”. Both forms of this variety were exported but about 80% of dry dates of Aseel variety was exported to India, where being used in religious activities. The advanced countries reject our date’s fruit because of infestation by pest and presence residue of pesticide drugs.

In our study we observed the chemical analysis of different nutrients, such as moisture, ash and total sugar in grams percentage of different stored date fruits. The results of moisture showed that the semi-dry dates Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel and Fasli content 23, 20, 15 and 14% moisture respectively, while the moisture in dry dates Aseel and Dadhi was content 10%. In different date varieties the moisture content ranged between 10-23% was recorded. The maximum moisture was found in Kupro semi-dry date 23% and minimum in Aseel and Dadhi dry varieties 10%. It indicates that the semi-dry dates have higher moisture than dry date’s varieties. Our results of moisture are almost same with previous reporters working on different date varieties. The moisture can vary between 9.2 to 30.1% [23, 24]. Moisture content was also in various varieties of date palm fruit the ranged between 10-30% [25]. The percentage of moisture level is different in dry varieties ranged from 7.58-12.56% [26]. The moisture percentage is different in date varieties ranged from 9.2-23.1%. A variation in moisture content of different date varieties at various mature stages, at ripening Tamar stage moisture ranged from 15 to 25 percentages [27]. Semi-dry dates possessed more 30% moisture and less than 10% in dry dates at Tamar stage [28].

The results of ash showed that the semi-dry date varieties content 1.35, 1.80, 1.95, 1.40% of ash, while the dry dates content 1.70, 1.65% of ash respectively, in different date varieties the ash ranged between 1.35-1.95% observed. The result of ash percentage was low in Aseel dry dates 1.70 % than the Aseel semi-dry dates which had 1.95%. The Aseel semi-dry dates contained the highest percentage of ash and the lowest percentage was recorded in Kupro semi-dry dates. Our results of ash are almost same and agreed with findings of other scientists working on different date varieties in which the ash percentage in different dry date varieties ranged between 1.62-1.98% [26, 27] reported that ash content in different date varieties ranged from 0.3-2.4%.

The results of present study are in closely agreeable and equivalent to the conclusion of research work conducted by earlier scientists. The difference in moisture and ash percentage has been reported among various varieties producing in same country or same variety in different areas, mostly due to the differences in harvest and post harvest skills, due to this resulting in different moisture level. The results content of moisture indicate that the high percent moisture content will facilitate spoilage of date fruits and low moisture percent will lead to dry dates not suitable to consumers. But dry dates could store for a long time compare to semi-dry dates because due to low moisture content dates prevent growing of yeast and molds. However, the moisture was decreased stage to stage, at ripening Tamar stage moisture around 24% for entering

the preservation reported by [29].

The total sugar we observed in semi-dry date varieties 85.90, 80.55, 73.35, 70.80% respectively, while the dry dates content 65.50% of total sugar. The flesh of semi-dry date Kupro variety showed a higher percentage of total sugar content 85.90% than dry date varieties Aseel and Dadhi 65.50%. Because date fruit was harvest before ripening stage and that fruit was boiled in very hot water then carry out spread in open sky in the light of sun leave them 3 to 5 days after that ready dry dates called “Chuhara” that is why dry dates content low percent of sugar. While the date fruit was harvest at Tamar stage and then dried it directly on the heat of sun that ready semi-dry dates called “Khajoor”.

The results of total sugar in the present study are agreed with the previous findings of research workers. Total sugar in different date varieties ranged between 70.87-83.80% [26]. Chemical analysis of four date varieties were grown in Saudi Arabia and reported that the total sugar ranged between 50-65% [30]. The fruit of dates is sweeter at last Tamar stage, because at this stage fruit was harvest and stored, so the results were supported by the findings of [31] who reported that at early kimri stage dates content low amount of sugar but at full ripening stage Tamar all sucrose converted into glucose and fructose (simple sugar), at this stage dates content 65 to 75 % of sugar. Saudi Arab date varieties contained about 70% reducing sugar with a approximately equal quantity of glucose and fructose [32]. During the maturation stage of date fruit tannins and moisture content decreases but sugar content increases, this makes fruit edible and tasty [33, 34]. However, the low moisture content and high sugar percent the dates can be saved and resistant to fungal spoilage after harvest. These data revealed that the dates fruit containing the most of essential nutritional material which is necessary to human metabolism and saving their life. The dates are very sweet but even then they have low level of lipids in comparison to sugar. Therefore, the date palm fruit is saving to heart and blood patients. Bedouin Arabs, who eat dates on a regular basis, show an extremely low rate of cancer and heart diseases. Actually sugar is an important component, since it immediately brings energizing the available calories.

CONCLUSION

It was observed that the date palm fruit is known for its nutritional values. The sugar, minerals and vitamins make the date-palm fruit a first class food, due to this; it is also called a complete food, because mostly all food nutrients are present. In many ways, date palm fruit may be considered as an ideal food, providing a wide range of essential nutrients and potential health benefits. In addition, the date palm fruit has potential in various aspects of the human biology such as; controlling diseases and activate the metabolism of the human body.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are much thankful to Centre for Biodiversity and Conservation, (Herbarium) SALU – Khairpur for conducting research work and photography, and stores, market and Mandy of Khairpur Mir's and Sukkur, Sindh for providing the samples of ripped and stored fruits of different varieties of date palm i.e., Kupro, Karbalian, Aseel, Fasl (semi-dry dates) and Aseel and Dadhi (dry dates).

REFERENCES

1. D.R. Lee, 1993. Date cultivation in the Choachella valley California. The Ohio J. Sci., 36(2): 82-87.
2. M. Riad, 2006. The date palm sector in Egypt; CIHEAM-options Mediterraneannes, 45-53.
3. R.W. Nixon, 1959. Growing dates in the United States; No. 207, U.S Dept, Agric, Government printing office, Washington, 50 p.
4. D.M. Jandan, 1974. Studied of some characters of important varieties of date-palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) grown in Khairpur Mirs. M.Sc Thesis, Univ. Sindh, Jamshoro.
5. Alabdulhadi, 2004. Date palm- A potential food security in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia- Research and development-<http://www.tropentage.de/2004/proceeding/node145.html>.
6. A.S. Hussein, G.A. Alhadrami, Y.H. Khalil, 1998. The use of dates and date pits in broiler starter and finisher diets. Bio Resource Technology, 66: 219-223.
7. M. Al-Farsi, C. Alasalvar, M. Al-Abid, K. Al-Shoaily, M. Al-Amry, F. Al-Rawahy, 2007. Compositional characteristics of dates, syrups, and there by-products. Food Chemistry, 104: 943-947.
8. M. Al-Farsi, C. Alasalvar, A. Morris, M. Baron, F. Shahidi, 2005. Composition and sensory characteristics of three native sun-dried date palm varieties grown in Oman. J. Agric. Food Chem., 53 (19): 7592-7599.
9. M. Ishtiaq, A. Tariq, A. Khalid, 1988. Physical properties of the fruit of some indigenous date palm cultivars grown at D.I.Khan. Sarhad J. Agric., 4(3): 271-274.
10. A.J. Beker, 1972. The date palm. A review of its past, present and recent advance in its culture industry and trade. Al-watan Publ., 1085 p.
11. Al-Dosari, A. Saleh, A. M.Al. Suhaibani, A.G. Ali, 2002. Susceptibility of some dry date palm varieties to infestation by *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) in relatio to their chemical composition. College of Foods and Agri. Sci. King Saud Uni. Repository. <http://hdl.handle.net/123456789/10531>.
12. S.A. Bhambhro, 2003. Insect pests ravage red date palm trees. Dawn news Pakistan.
13. M. Amin, S. Zafar, A. Anum, 2007. Potential o dates export. Daily Dawn. May 07.
14. N. Chaira, A. Ferchichi, A. Mrabet, M. Sghairoun, 2007. Chemical composition of flesh and the pit of date palm fruit and radical scavenging activity at their extract. Pak. J. Bio. Sci., 10: 2202-2207.
15. AOAC, 2000. Official methods of analysis. 17th ed., Association of Official Analytical Chemists. Arlington, VA, USA. 2200 p.
16. AOAC, 1990. Association of official Analytical Chemists. Official Methods of Analysis, Washington, D.C.
17. M.M. Shukr, 1983. Determination of date moisture content: A review. Date palm J., 2(2).
18. A.G. Woodman, 1941. Food analysis, (McGraw Hill Book company Inc.). 18 p.
19. M. Dubois, J.K. Gilles, P.A. Hamilton, P.A. Rebers, F. Smith, 1956. Colorimetric method for determination of sugar and related substances, Analytical Chemistry, 28(3): 350-356.
20. G.S. Markhand, 1991. Effect of pollen from different male cultivars of date palm on the quantitative characters and ripening of the fruit of Aseel variety. M.Phil Thesis, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur.
21. M.K. Khushk, M.A. Quresshi, M.S. Memon. 2004. General features and properties of date palm fruit of Khairpur. Sci. Sindh, 11: 67-75.
22. G.S. Markhand, A.A. Abul Soad, 2007. Fruit characterization of Pakistani dates. The fourth symposium on date palm in Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia.
23. I. Booij, G. Piombo, J.M. Risterucci, M. Coupe, D. Thomas, M. Ferry, 1992. Study on the chemical composition of dates at different stages of maturity for the varietal characterization of

- various cultivars of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) Fruits. 47: 667-678.
24. I.A. Ahmed, A.K. Ahmed, R.K. Robinson, 1995. Chemical composition of date varieties as Influenced by the stage of ripening. *Food Chemistry*, 54: 305-309.
 25. K.K. Aidoo, R.F. Tesster, J.E. Morison, D. Macfurlane, 1996. The composition and microbial quality of pre-packed dates purchased in greater Glasgow. *Intr. J. Food Sci. Tech.*, 311: 433-438.
 26. B.R. Ramadan, 1995. Preparation and evaluation of Egyptian date syrup. *Food Science & Technology Dept.*, Faculty of Agric. Assuit Univ. Assuit, Egypt.
 27. W. Al-Shahib, R.M. Marshal, 2003. The fruit of the date palm: its possible uses as the best food for the future. *Intr. J. Food Sci. Nutr.*, 54: 247-259.
 28. M. Abdessalam, F.C. Ali, C. Nizar, S.M. Ben, B. Mohammad, M.P. Threadgill, 2008. Physio-chemical characteristics and total utility of date palm varieties grown in the southern of Tunisia. *Pak. J. Bio. Sci.*, 11 (7): 1003-1008.
 29. M.S.H. Ahmed, 1981. Investigation on insect disinfestations of dried dates by using gama radiation- A review. *Date Palm J. I.*, 107-116 p.
 30. M.A. Shaheen, A.D. Al-Qurashi, 2007. Fruit chemical composition and its correlation with some date palm cultivars during fruit development stages. *JKAU: Met. Env. and Arid Land Agric. Sci.*, 18: 19-26.
 31. R.H. Myhara, A. AL-Alawi, J. Karkalas, M.S. Taylor, 2000. Sensory and textural changes in maturing Omani dates. *J. Sci. Food and Agric.*, 80: 2181-2185.
 32. M.S. Mikki, S.M. AL-Taisan, A.A. Abdul Azziz, 1989. Isolation and identification of the chemical constituents of the spathe of the date palm. *Al-Hassa Regional Agric. Research Centre, Hofuf, Saudi Arabia.*
 33. A.G. Tafti, M.H. Fooladi, 2005. Hanges in physical and chemical characteristics of Mozafati date fruit during development. *J. Bio. Si.*, 5: 319-322.
 34. A.G. Tafti, M.H. Fooladi, 2006. Physico-chemical properties of Iranian Shamsaei date at different stages of maturity. *World J. Dairy and Food Sci.*, 1(1): 28-32.

Citation: Sahito HA *et al.* (2017). Varietal analyze of chemical composition moisture, ash and sugar of date palm fruits, *J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology*. V5I1. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V5I1.03

Copyright: © 2017 Sahito HA, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.